

A two-step computational aeroacoustics method applied to high-speed flows

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This study numerically investigates the generated noise and perturbation fields from an excited high-speed jet flow (air), which is modeled by the linearized Euler equations. The mean flow is prescribed by experimental-analytical approach. Harmonic hydrodynamic excitation is applied at the nozzle exit to mimic a previous experimental setup, and to enhance the periodic component of the perturbation field. We investigate the propagation of this excitation in the pressure (acoustic), velocity, and density waves, looking at details that were not addressed in the experiments. We integrate the governing equations using the finite-difference method and a special scheme that is second-order accurate in time and fourth-order accurate in space. Alternating one-sided differences are implemented to eliminate spatial biases in the calculations. We use an appropriate set of boundary conditions that minimizes spurious reflections, including the characteristics-based Thompson inflow, acoustic radiation, Tam and Webb outflow, and centerline conditions. We investigate the characteristics of these waves, including the spatial growth and damping, and the noise radiation pattern. © 2008 Institute of Noise Control Engineering.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Exhaust gases emitted from breathing and non-breathing engines are examples of free jet flows, which are encountered in different industrial applications, such as gas turbine engines and rocket motors. Better performance in these applications is associated with higher jet speeds, which imply more noise emissions. Testing of a typical-size jet engine is accompanied by noise levels of about 140 dB¹, whereas they can be 130 dB at a distance of 50 ft (15.2 m) from a military jet aircraft at take-off from aircraft carrier with afterburner². These noise levels are far beyond the human tolerance (about 100 dB³). In fact, the exposure to noise levels above 125 dB can be painful and may result in sudden, temporary deafness¹. This motivated a lot of research to predict and mitigate noise emissions from free jets. This study is focused on numerical noise prediction of high-speed free jet flows and on the properties of the associated perturbation and acoustic fields.

Computational aeroacoustics (CAA) simulations typically involve issues that might not be significant in

traditional computational fluid dynamics (CFD). Special attention should be paid to the numerical implementation as we are interested in the noise emission rather than the flow motion or the thermal field. Aeroacoustics is concerned with the sound generated by the motion of gases. This motion induces pressure perturbations which are heard if they are strong enough and fall within the audible human spectrum. Accurate prediction of noise is a building block in the process of noise control or the design of devices with low noise. Computational aeroacoustics has proven to be a reliable tool to predict and simulate noise generation for different classes of problems⁴⁻⁸. Computational aeroacoustics problems differ from classical computational fluid dynamics ones in various aspects. This is ascribed to the unique nature of CAA which attempts to capture unsteady low-amplitude waves, whereas industrial CFD commonly attempts to capture steady fields or large-amplitude variations. In addition to that, CAA is concerned with acoustic propagation in the far field thus requires large computational domains. The CFD analysis usually focuses on the near-wall region in order to calculate the forces and moments exerted by the flow field on the structures in contact with the fluid. Also, with the wide range of scales in the audible frequencies (20 Hz to 20 kHz), it becomes necessary to extend the simulation for long

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times to capture the low-frequency waves which might have relatively very long periods. These issues motivated researchers to develop special techniques that suit CAA problems more than classical CFD counterparts.

There are different approaches used in CAA, with different levels of accuracy and computational cost. In the following, we will briefly go over the main ones and highlight some representative examples of each approach. The direct numerical simulation (DNS) approach integrates the compressible Navier-Stokes equations to resolve the flow quantities directly without any modeling or simplifying decomposition. This method is limited to a certain range of problems due to the tremendous computational time and power needed. It is more suitable as a validation tool of other simplified approaches⁹ or to study the underlying physics of the problem. Freund¹⁰ is one of the researchers who utilized the DNS approach in CAA. He computed the flow field and the associated acoustic field of a subsonic cold jet, with Mach number 0.9 and Reynolds number (Re) 3,600. The calculated pressure field was used to compute the Lighthill acoustic source. Good agreement was reported between the Lighthill's analogy and the DNS approach. However, the difference in the amount of computations between the Lighthill analytical approach and the DNS numerical approach is substantial. Owis and Balakumar¹¹ used DNS to compute the jet noise of an axisymmetric subsonic cold jet, with Mach 0.85 and Re 2,500, and supersonic cold jet, with Mach 1.5 and Re 1.27×10^6 . They used MacCormack schemes and different nonreflecting boundary conditions that are based on the method of characteristics, asymptotic analysis of the governing equations, buffer domain technique, and matching layer. Tam and Ju¹² applied the DNS to another CAA problem, which is the prediction of tones emitted from a NACA0012 airfoil with a symmetric rounded trailing edge at Re 2×10^5 and low angles of attack from 2° to 8° .

Large eddy simulation (LES) is a simplified level of the Navier-Stokes approach, where the flow field is decomposed into large scales and small, subgrid, scales. Tam¹³ dedicated a study to discuss the feasibility of applying LES to aeroacoustic problems. He concluded that LES is not yet a good approach to handle most of the aeroacoustics problems (such as airframe noise, and fan and turbomachinery noise) due to the complexity of both the geometry and the flow fields in these problems. At that time (1998), he proposed that LES may find near term application in high-speed jet noise. However, he emphasized the resolution limitations when applying LES to jet problems. For example, adequate resolution to study a

typical commercial jet engine requires 2.1×10^9 grid points, which (if available) is not suitable for engineering design and analysis applications since the demanded resources and elapsed times are tremendous. Nevertheless, there are continuous attempts to use LES in jet and mixing layer noise problems. Some of them use LES to compute both the turbulence region (in the near field) and the acoustic radiation (in the far field), such as Bogey et al.¹⁴ Others limit the use of LES to the near field only and use an analytical method (e.g., Lighthill's acoustic analogy, Kirchhoff method, or the Ffowcs Williams-Hawkings surface integral method) to predict the noise in the far field, such as Zhao et al.¹⁵ and Lo et al.¹⁶

As proposed by Tam¹³ in his study about the LES feasibility, Goldstein¹⁷ combined the LES approach, which is still too expensive for many industrial applications, with another more-simplified approach. The latter is the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS), which are based on temporal decomposition in contrast to the spatial decomposition of LES. In the RANS approach, the flow field is decomposed into time-averaged and turbulent fields. The time-averaged field is resolved directly, whereas the turbulent one is modeled. In the proposed hybrid approach, the transition occurs from RANS-based modeling near the nozzle lip to LES-based modeling downstream. The low-frequency sound waves are directly resolved by the hybrid approach, whereas the residual small-scale high-frequency waves are computed through modeling the source terms via linear equations. This approach was motivated by the fact that acoustic contribution from the subgrid scales in LES are not accounted for. Decreasing the size of these scales, by refining the grid, solves this problem but incurs heavy demands for computational resources.

If viscous effects are insignificant, the viscous terms in the Navier-Stokes equations can be dropped, which results in the Euler equations. Then, the flow field can be split into mean and perturbation fields. Provided that the mean flow is known, the perturbation field will be governed by the linearized form of Euler equations (LEE). The accuracy of such splitting increases if the amplitude of the perturbation field is small compared to the mean one, which is a typical feature of acoustic fields as compared to the aerodynamic fields. Ali et al.¹⁸ used this approach to simulate the two-dimensional acoustic field induced by the flow over a forward facing step. This problem can be used to approximate the radiated noise due to the mounted power supply units on top of a high-speed train. The authors started from the Euler equations in its nonconservative form and got the LEE equations in a two-dimensional Cartesian system. We will consider

the conservative form of the equations and in axisymmetric coordinates. That is why the form of the LEE we will formulate here is different from what the authors solved. The source term was the time derivative of the mean-flow pressure, which was provided simultaneously to the LEE solver from an LES solver for the mean-flow. The Re (based on the step height) was 8,000. The present study uses the linearized Euler equations to model and compute the perturbation field associated with supersonic axisymmetric jet flow. Harmonic excitation of hydrodynamic form is applied in the potential core of the mean flow which amplifies downstream, saturates, and then decays. We investigate the acoustic field in this problem. We also study the similarities and differences between the pressure (acoustic) waves and the velocity or density waves.

2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Navier-Stokes equations fully model the jet motion. By dropping the viscous terms in these equations, we get the Euler equations. In the considered free shear flows, large-scale dynamics are the main sound source in supersonic¹⁹ and even in high-speed subsonic²⁰ jets. Viscous effects for these scales are negligible and inviscid calculations can be quite successful in capturing the main wave features in free shear flows²¹. So, an Euler-based method is a good candidate for noise prediction in this type of problems. Although Euler equations represent a simplified form of the Navier-Stokes counterparts, both contain the nonlinear (inertia) terms. Linearizing these equations is another simplification that remarkably reduces the computational work needed to integrate the resulting governing system (linearized Euler equations, LEE). It is important to mention here that these simplifications restrict the applicability of the simplified model. However, if the implied conditions are met, the simplified model should be capable of capturing most of the characteristics that are obtained by the more expensive models. For acoustic simulations, the perturbations amplitudes are typically much smaller than the mean-flow ones. This renders linearized models a feasible simulation approach. In fact, the linearization technique is used in many fields outside fluid mechanics and aeroacoustics. For example, it is used to reduce complicated structural models into simple linear ones provided that the deflections are small.

Given a general flow variable, b , we can represent it as the sum of two quantities: the mean (time averaged), B , and the perturbation (fluctuating), b' as follows:

$$b = B + b' \quad (1)$$

where B is assumed to be known and the goal is to solve for b' . After solving for the perturbation quantity,

we can add it to the mean one to find the total quantity. However, in the present study, we are merely interested in the perturbation field since the pressure perturbations (propagating pressure waves) form the acoustic field and noise emissions. Applying Eqn. (1) to the primitive variables; which are the density (ρ), axial velocity component (u), radial velocity component (v), total (i.e., internal plus kinetic) specific energy (e), and pressure (p) results in:

$$\rho(x,r,t) = \mathfrak{R}(x,r) + \rho'(x,r,t) \quad (2a)$$

$$u(x,r,t) = U(x,r) + u'(x,r,t) \quad (2b)$$

$$v(x,r,t) = V(x,r) + v'(x,r,t) \quad (2c)$$

$$e(x,r,t) = E(x,r) + e'(x,r,t) \quad (2d)$$

$$p(x,r,t) = P(x,r) + p'(x,r,t) \quad (2e)$$

It is worth mentioning here that while the mean-flow field in the present problem is time independent, it can be time varying in other situations, such as the case of a flow field around oscillating structures. Since we are interested in axisymmetric jets, all equations are written and solved in an axisymmetric coordinate system (x, r), where x is the axial coordinate (aligned with the jet and nozzle centerline) and r is the radial coordinate. The origin is located along the centerline at the nozzle exit. To derive the linearized Euler equations, we start from the axisymmetric Navier-Stokes equations in their conservative vector form, which is:

$$\frac{\partial\{Q\}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial\{F\}}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\{G\})}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r}\{S\} + \frac{\partial\{F_v\}}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\{G_v\})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r}\{S_v\} \quad (3)$$

where $\{Q\}$ is the conservative-variables vector, $\{F\}$ and $\{F_v\}$ are the inviscid and viscous axial momentum-flux vectors, $\{G\}$ and $\{G_v\}$ are the inviscid and viscous radial momentum-flux vectors, and $\{S\}$ and $\{S_v\}$ are the inviscid and viscous source-term vectors. These source terms arise as a result of transforming the equations from Cartesian coordinates (where there are no source terms) to axisymmetric coordinates.

Upon dropping the viscous terms from Eqn. (3), we get the axisymmetric Euler equations in their conservative vector form, which is:

$$\frac{\partial\{Q\}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial\{F\}}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\{G\})}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r}\{S\} \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{Bmatrix} \rho \\ \rho u \\ \rho v \\ \rho e \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{Bmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + p \\ \rho uv \\ (\rho e + p)u \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \begin{Bmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + p \\ (\rho e + p)v \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{r} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ p \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4b)$$

Applying the splitting in Eqns. (1) and (2) to Eqn. (4b) and then subtracting the equations governing the mean-flow field, which are:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathfrak{R} \\ \mathfrak{R}U \\ \mathfrak{R}V \\ \mathfrak{R}E \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathfrak{R}U \\ \mathfrak{R}U^2 + P \\ \mathfrak{R}UV \\ (\mathfrak{R}E + P)U \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathfrak{R}V \\ \mathfrak{R}UV \\ \mathfrak{R}V^2 + P \\ (\mathfrak{R}E + P)V \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{r} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ P \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

gives the following linearized Euler equations, whose conservative vector from is:

$$\frac{\partial \{Q'\}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \{F'\}}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r\{G'\})}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r} \{S'\} \quad (6a)$$

where: $\{Q'\}$ is the vector of perturbation of the conservative variables

$$\{Q'\}: \begin{Bmatrix} \rho' \\ (\rho u)' \\ (\rho v)' \\ (\rho e)' \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6b)$$

$\{F'\}$ is the vector of perturbation of the axial momentum flux

$$\{F'\}: \begin{Bmatrix} (\rho u)' \\ -\rho' U^2 + 2(\rho u)' U + p' \\ -\rho' UV + (\rho v)' U + (\rho u)' V \\ U(p' + (\rho e)') + ((\rho u)' - \rho' U) \left(\frac{P}{\mathfrak{R}} + E \right) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6c)$$

$\{G'\}$ is the vector of perturbation of the radial momentum flux

$$\{G'\}: \begin{Bmatrix} (\rho v)' \\ -\rho' UV + (\rho v)' U + (\rho u)' V \\ -\rho' V^2 + 2(\rho v)' V + p' \\ V(p' + (\rho e)') + ((\rho v)' - \rho' V) \left(\frac{P}{\mathfrak{R}} + E \right) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6d)$$

$\{S'\}$ is the vector of perturbation of the source term

$$\{S'\}: \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ p' \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6e)$$

Equations (6a)–(6e) represents a linear system of hyperbolic partial differential equations that governs the perturbation field, with coefficients that are obtained from the mean-flow field. We solve a normalized version of this system using a reference length, velocity, and density that are based on the jet-exit conditions.

3 FIRST STEP: MEAN FIELD

3.1 Description of the Experimental Study

As mentioned in the previous section, the mean (time-averaged) field is needed in order to solve the equations governing the perturbation (fluctuating) field. For this purpose, we use a mean flow based on the measurements of Trout²² and Trout and McLaughlin²³ for a near-isentropic supersonic cold jet at Mach number 2.1 and Reynolds number 70,000 (based on the conditions of the jet at the nozzle exit). A glow-discharge device located at a distance of 0.4 nozzle radius (R_j) from the nozzle exit was used to excite the flow. Similar excitation technique was used by Kendall²⁴ to study the instability of supersonic boundary layer. The purpose of the excitation in the experiment was to develop an understanding of the nature of more-organized perturbations within the jet by enhancing the periodic component of the perturbed field as compared to the random one. To better illustrate this, the general perturbation flow quantity b' in Eqn. (1) can be decomposed into:

$$b'(x, r, t) = \tilde{b}(x, r, t) + b''(x, r, t) \quad (7a)$$

where

$$\tilde{b}(x, r, t) = \tilde{b}(x, r, t + T) \quad (7b)$$

and T is the period of the excitation. In the experiment, the periodic excitation was implemented by attaching a tungsten electrode (with a diameter of $0.1R_j$) insulated by a ceramic sleeve and held in the nozzle wall by a

Fig. 1—Typical supersonic free jet with the main dimensions and regions.

press fit brass outer sleeve. An electric AC signal with 700 Volts peak-to-peak was applied with a negative bias of 400 Volts. The breakdown voltage was approximately 600 Volts, thus a small glow of ionized air was turning on and off at the excitation frequency. This excitation frequency, which is the discharge frequency, was attained using an audio generator and a power amplifier. While the temporal development of the excitation was not given in the studies of Trout²² and Trout and McLaughlin,²³ a previous study by McLaughlin et al.²⁵ used a similar exciter (but with an AC signal of 800 Volts peak-to-peak and a negative bias of 450 Volts) showed a snapshot of the oscilloscope trace of the exciter signal, which was near sinusoidal. The jet radius R_j was 5 mm.

3.2 Analytical Representation of the Measurements

Tam and Burton²⁶ proposed continuous functions coupled with conservation laws in order to fit the aforementioned measurements accurately. We are using this technique to compute the needed mean-flow field. The mean-flow solution for other jets can be obtained by solving the boundary layer equations for wakes²⁷, which yield a reasonable mean-flow profile. This step will be a minor part of the overall process; the major part will be the computation of the perturbation field since high accuracy is required in that step. Figure 1 shows an illustration of the supersonic free jet, which is divided axially into two regions: the uniform-core region and the fully-developed similarity region. The uniform core is characterized by having uniform, as indicated from its name, mean axial velocity at each axial position. It extends to $x=16R_j$ (i.e., 8 nozzle diameters after the nozzle). It has a converging near-conical shape with a decreasing radius of $h(x)$. This region can itself be divided into two parts: poten-

Fig. 2—Variations of the computed uniform core and mixing layer dimensions: $h(x)$, $r(0.5)$, and $b(x)$. The measured values of $b(x)$ are superimposed.

tial core and transition. The potential core extends to $x=10R_j$. It is dominated by potential flow with uniform mean axial velocity that is equal to the jet exit velocity (U_j). Thus, in the potential core, the centerline mean axial velocity ($U_C(x)$) is constant and equals to U_j . In the transitional part of the uniform-core region, the mean axial velocity is decreasing, but it is still uniform at each axial position. Outside the uniform core, the shear (or mixing) layer exists, where the axial velocity decreases in the radial direction with a half-Gaussian profile. When the shear layer overlaps axially with the uniform core ($x < 16R_j$), it has a diverging annular shape with an increasing thickness $b(x)$. When there is no overlap ($x \geq 16R_j$), the shear layer has a diverging near-conical shape with radius $b(x)$. The radial distance from the centerline to the point where $U(x,r) = 1/2U_C(x)$ is denoted by $r(0.5)$. The relation: $r(0.5) = b(x) + h(x)$ applies at any axial position, but the relation: $r(0.5) = b(x)$ applies only in the fully-developed region since $h(x) = 0$ there. With this description, the following expressions are used to describe the mean axial velocity:

$$U(x,r) = \begin{cases} U_C(x) & r < h(x) \\ U_C(x) \exp \left[-\ln(2) \left(\frac{r-h(x)}{b(x)} \right)^2 \right] & r \geq h(x) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Careful attention is paid while computing $U_C(x)$, $h(x)$, and $b(x)$ so that the axial momentum is conserved. Other expressions exist for the rest of the mean-flow quantities (i.e., radial velocity, density, temperature, and pressure) based on mass and energy conservation as well as the equation of state. Figure 2 gives the axial distribution of the computed $h(x)$,

Fig. 3—Variation of the normalized centerline axial velocity (fitted and measured).

$r(0.5)$, and $b(x)$. The same figure shows measured values of $b(x)$, which indicate the good performance of the analytical technique we use here. Figure 3 compares the fitted and measured normalized centerline mean axial velocity ($U_c(x)/U_j$), and shows how good the curve fitting is. The potential core can be identified in this figure by the condition $U_c(x)/U_j=1$. Figure 4 shows axial distributions at different radial distances of the mean axial Mach number, which is defined as U/a , where $a(x,r)=\sqrt{\gamma P/\mathfrak{R}}$ is the mean acoustic speed (speed of sound), and γ is the specific heat ratio of the jet (air), which is constant ($\gamma=1.4$).

4 SECOND STEP: PERTURBATION FIELD

4.1 Perturbations of Primitive Variables

The perturbation field is governed by the system in Eqns. (6a)–(6e). We integrate this system numerically in time and obtain the development of the perturbation

Fig. 4—Variations of the mean axial Mach number at different radial distances.

field. The conservative system in Eqns. (6a)–(6e) yields the perturbation of the density, ρ' , and the conservative perturbation quantities: $(\rho u)'$, $(\rho v)'$, and $(\rho e)'$. They are used along with the mean-flow field to extract the perturbation of the primitive variables: u' , v' , and p' . This is achieved through the following relations:

$$(\rho u)' = \rho' U + \mathfrak{R} u' \quad (9a)$$

$$(\rho v)' = \rho' V + \mathfrak{R} v' \quad (9b)$$

$$(\rho e)' = \frac{p'}{\gamma-1} + ((\rho u)' U + (\rho v)' V) - \frac{1}{2} \rho' (U^2 + V^2) \quad (9c)$$

In Eqn. (9c), the first term: $p' / (\gamma-1)$ represents the perturbation of the specific internal energy (energy per unit volume), whereas the last two terms: $((\rho u)' U + (\rho v)' V) - 1/2 \rho' (U^2 + V^2)$ represent the perturbation of the specific kinetic energy.

Equation (9) can be solved for u' , v' , and p' as:

$$u' = \frac{(\rho u)' - \rho' U}{\mathfrak{R}} \quad (10a)$$

$$v' = \frac{(\rho v)' - \rho' V}{\mathfrak{R}} \quad (10b)$$

$$p' = (\gamma-1) \left((\rho e)' - ((\rho u)' U + (\rho v)' V) + \frac{1}{2} \rho' (U^2 + V^2) \right) \quad (10c)$$

4.2 Grid

For the acoustic problem, the computational domain extends to $x=70R_j$ and $r=32R_j$. This includes a reasonable propagation region of the perturbation waves. In the axial direction, the spacing is uniform with $\Delta x = R_j/6$; this requires 421 stations along the axial direction. In the experimental study, it was reported that the wavenumber of the perturbation of the axial mass-velocity: $(\rho u)'$, measured by hot-wire, is $k \approx 0.8/R_j$ (but no figures or details about the temporal development of any perturbation wave were given, which we will address here). We confirmed this in our simulations, which can be considered another validation test. The wavenumber is related to the wavelength (λ) as:

$$k \equiv \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) suggests that the wavelength of these waves is $7.9R_j$. Since the density and velocity pertur-

Fig. 5—Radial profile of the grid: step size versus the radial coordinate (both are normalized with respect to R_j).

bation waves are convected with the mean flow, they will dominantly propagate in a near-axial direction. Thus, the resolution of capturing these waves is directly related to Δx . The current grid yields about 47 points per wavelength (PPW), which is a high value compared to the commonly-used resolutions. For example, Konno et al.²⁸ used 10 PPW to simulate the two-dimensional sound wave propagation in air. Hall et al.²⁹ used 11 PPW to solve the LEE for the propagation and absorption of noise in a rectangular lined duct and got good agreement with the measurements.

In the radial direction, the grid is clustered by a factor of 1/1.02 within the critical layer ($r < R_j$) and then stretched outside it by a factor of 1.02. This nonuniformity is necessary to capture the high gradients in this region. At the radial location where $\Delta r = \Delta x$, the radial spacing becomes uniform for the remaining portion of the domain. This is illustrated in Fig. 5. This distribution of the grid required the distribution of 298 points in the radial direction.

4.3 Overview of the Numerical Scheme

Computational aeroacoustics require very accurate numerical schemes and boundary treatments since they inherently try to capture small-amplitude fields. So, a classical scheme used for fluid dynamics problems might be unsatisfactory for the present study. In particular, excessive dissipation and considerable dispersion properties of the numerical scheme need to be very weak. These properties tend to damp the acoustic oscillations or to generate nonphysical oscillations that might affect the acoustic field significantly. While small dissipation is a favorable property of a numerical scheme since it enhances its stability, excessive dissipation is very unfavorable since it means that the numerically-calculated derivatives are smaller than the

exact ones. Thus, the gradients of the physical problem are attenuated. Numerical schemes inevitably exhibit some level of dispersion. This results in a phase shift between the calculated derivatives and the exact ones. In acoustics problems, this adversely affects the resolved waves. However, dispersion can be mitigated by using small time steps or high-order schemes. Both dispersion and dissipation increase as the frequency of the resolved waves increases.

We use an extended version of the MacCormack³⁰ predictor-corrector scheme that is second order in time and fourth order in space. This scheme was proposed by Gottlieb and Turkel³¹ based on the classical 2-2 MacCormack scheme (i.e., it is second order-accurate in both time and space). The spatial accuracy was improved by increasing the stencil size from three points to five points. While later high-order schemes for aeroacoustics problems; such as the high-order essentially non-oscillatory (ENO) schemes by Atkins³², the compact finite difference schemes by Lele³³, and the explicit dispersion-relation-preserving (DRP) scheme by Tam and Webb³⁴. This is in addition to the Runge-Kutta family of schemes (for temporal integration only). However, the 2-4 scheme of Gottlieb and Turkel (GT24) continues to be used successfully³⁵⁻³⁷ in computational aeroacoustics applications since it has favorable stability and because it is an explicit scheme, thus does not require inversion of large matrices (like the sixth-order compact scheme), which is equivalent to less computational and memory demands. Ragab and Sheen³⁸ used this scheme for studying nonlinear instability problems in mixing layers with supersonic phase speed.

Goodrich³⁹ did the most extensive comparison between numerical schemes that are especially used in CAA. In his comparative study, more than twenty schemes with different temporal and spatial orders of accuracy (from first order to eleventh order in both time and space) were examined. These schemes included the space-time conservation element and solution element⁴⁰ (2-2), GT24 (2-4), MacCormack (2-2), Lax-Wendroff (2-2), Runge-Kutta (4, 6, and 8 stages) with fourth-order central difference for spatial derivatives, modified expansion solution approximation (MESA)⁴¹ methods that are based on high-order central methods (4-4, 6-6, 8-8), and high-order methods with Hermitian interpolation⁴²⁻⁴⁴ (1-1, 3-3, 5-5, 7-7, 9-9, 11-11). Two benchmark problems were considered. In both of them, the one-dimensional isentropic linearized Euler equations were solved to predict the propagation of a pressure wave, where the exact solution is known. These problems are very relevant to the present study. The first benchmark was for a sine wave with an initial condition of $p'(x, t=0) = \sin(\pi x)$, whereas the second

was for an exponential one with an initial condition of $p'(x, t=0) = \exp(-10 \sin^2(\pi x))$, which is more challenging. Different values of the time step (Δt) and grid spacing (Δx) were used with a fixed ratio of $\Delta x / \Delta t = 2$. In terms of computational cost, the GT24 ranked third in terms of the number of FLOPS (Floating point Operations Per Second) per grid point, per time step (24 FLOPS) after the 1-1 Hermitian interpolation scheme (16 FLOPS), and the 2-2 Lax-Wendroff (18 FLOPS). The 2-2 space-time conservation element and solution element requires 64 FLOPS, the 4-4 Runge-Kutta requires 72 FLOPS, and the 4-4 MESA method requires 44 FLOPS. These FLOPS values are based on the number of multiplication operations needed to advance the solution at one grid point over a complete time step. In terms of performance, the accuracy of the GT24 scheme was five times higher than the accuracy of the 2-2 Lax-Wendroff scheme (whose computational demands are 75% of the GT24 demands) and the 2-2 space-time conservation element and solution element (whose computational demands are 267% of the GT24 demands). With 16 grid points per wavelength, the GT24 had comparable accuracy with the 4-4 MESA scheme (whose computational demands are 183% of the GT24 demands). As the grid and time resolution increase, the 4-4 Runge-Kutta scheme outperforms the GT24 in terms of accuracy, although the GT24 remains satisfactory.

DeBonis and Scott⁴⁵ conducted another comparative study and evaluated the performance of the GT24 scheme versus the 4-4 Runge-Kutta scheme (RK44). Three benchmark problems were used in that study. The first benchmark problem was the linear inviscid one-dimensional convection problem ($\partial u / \partial t + \partial u / \partial x = 0$) of a Gaussian pulse with an initial condition of $u(x, t=0) = 1/2 \exp(-\ln(2)(x/3)^2)$. The second benchmark problem was the nonlinear version of the first problem ($\partial u / \partial t + \partial(u^2/2) / \partial x = 0$) with an initial condition of $u(x, t=0) = 1/8 \exp(-\ln(2)(x/10)^2)$. Although the occurrence of a shock is possible in the second benchmark problem due to the nonlinearity, the initial condition and the time range $0 \leq t \leq 100$ were adjusted such that the shock does not develop during the simulation. The third benchmark problem was similar to the second one, but different initial condition $u(x, t=0) = 1/2 \exp(-\ln(2)(x/5)^2)$ and time range $0 \leq t \leq 200$ were used such that a shock develops during the simulation. Different values of the time step Δt were tried for each scheme to estimate the maximum stable value. Then, various values of the grid spacing Δx were used. The comparisons showed that the GT24 scheme has better inherent stability properties than the RK44 scheme. For the third benchmark problem, the RK44 failed to give a stable solution and an artificial dissipa-

tion term was needed. Analytical investigation of both schemes interpreted this as a result of a dissipative term (proportional to the even derivative $\partial^4(u^2/2) / \partial x^4$) in the truncation error of the GT24 scheme. On the other hand, the RK44 allows larger Δt for stability (except for the third benchmark problem). While this is an important advantage, it is balanced by the extra computations needed by the RK44 scheme as compared to the GT24 scheme for same grid density. Also, in acoustics problems, large Δt might not be usable since the temporal resolution preferences (to capture the propagating waves adequately) can override the stability limitations when choosing Δt , as in the present study.

4.4 Discretization

The differential operator in Eqn. (6a) is split into x -operator and r -operator. The sequence of integrating these operators in one time step is reversed in the following time step. Therefore, a complete integration cycle is performed over two time steps rather than one. This reduces any directional bias in the solution. To demonstrate the details of the discretization, let us consider the following expression, which has four one-dimensional numerical integration operators to be applied in succession:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+2} = L_{2x} L_{2r} L_{1r} L_{1x} Q_{i,k}^n \quad (12)$$

where Q is same as $\{Q'\}$ in Eqn. (6b) (the prime and the curly brackets are dropped to simplify the coming expressions); the superscript n is the time-step index; the subscripts i and k are the grid-point indices in the axial and radial directions, respectively; the operators L_{1x} , L_{2x} , L_{1r} , and L_{2r} are one-dimensional and each one consists of a predictor and a corrector step, each of which uses one-sided difference. The operators L_{1x} and L_{2x} represent discrete time integration for grid points located along axial grid lines (when sweeping in the radial direction), whereas the operators L_{1r} and L_{2r} represent discrete time integration for grid points located along radial grid lines (when sweeping in the axial direction). These 4 operators are applied in the following sequence:

4.4.1 First operator: $Q^{n+1/2} = L_{1x} Q^n$

Keeping only the x -operator in Eqn. (6a), we get the following one-dimensional differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} \quad (13a)$$

where F is equivalent to $\{F'\}$ in Eqn. (6c). The predictor step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+1/4} = Q_{i,k}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta x} [7(F_i - F_{i-1}) - (F_{i-1} - F_{i-2})]_k^n \quad \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial r} \right)_{For} = \left(\frac{\Delta \eta}{-7r_k + 8r_{k+1} - r_{k+2}} \right)_i \quad (14e)$$

(13b)

$$\text{or } Q_{i,k}^{n+1/4} = Q_{i,k}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta x} [7F_i - 8F_{i-1} + F_{i-2}]_k^n \quad (13c)$$

The corrector step is:

$$Q_{i,j}^{n+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{i,k}^{n+1/4} + Q_{i,k}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta x} [7(F_{i+1} - F_i) - (F_{i+2} - F_{i+1})]_k^{n+1/4} \right) \quad (13d)$$

$$\text{or } Q_{i,k}^{n+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{i,k}^{n+1/4} + Q_{i,k}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta x} [-7F_i + 8F_{i+1} - F_{i+2}]_k^{n+1/4} \right) \quad (13e)$$

4.4.2 Second operator: $Q^{n+1} = L_{1r} Q^{n+1/2}$

Now, consider the one-dimensional differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial G}{\partial r} + S \quad (14a)$$

where G is equivalent to $\{G'\}$ in Eqn. (6d) and S is equivalent to $1/r\{S'\}$ in Eqn. (6e). The predictor step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+3/4} = Q_{i,k}^{n+1/2} - \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial r} \right)_{Back} \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta \eta} [7G_k - 8G_{k-1} + G_{k-2}]_i^{n+1/2} + \Delta t S_{i,k}^{n+1/2} \quad (14b)$$

The corrector step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{i,k}^{n+3/4} + Q_{i,k}^{n+1/2} - \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial r} \right)_{For} \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta \eta} [-7G_k + 8G_{k+1} - G_{k+2}]_i^{n+3/4} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} S_{i,k}^{n+3/4} \right) \quad (14c)$$

where $\Delta \eta$ is the spacing in the radial direction if the grid was uniform (here, $\Delta \eta = 32R_j/297$), $(\partial \eta / \partial r)_{Back}$ and $(\partial \eta / \partial r)_{For}$ are the metrics of transformation computed via backward and forward formulas similar to those used in the corresponding predictor or corrector steps, respectively. They are required due to the nonuniformity of the grid in the radial direction. Their expressions are:

$$\left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial r} \right)_{Back} = \left(\frac{\Delta \eta}{7r_k - 8r_{k-1} + r_{k-2}} \right)_i \quad (14d)$$

4.4.3 Third operator: $Q^{n+3/2} = L_{2r} Q^{n+1}$

This operator is similar to the second operator (L_{1r}), but the one-sided formulas are reversed. So, the predictor step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+5/4} = Q_{i,k}^{n+1} - \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial r} \right)_{For} \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta \eta} [-7G_k + 8G_{k+1} - G_{k+2}]_i^{n+1} + \Delta t S_{i,k}^{n+1} \quad (15a)$$

The corrector step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+3/2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{i,k}^{n+5/4} + Q_{i,k}^{n+3/2} - \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial r} \right)_{Back} \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta \eta} [7G_k - 8G_{k-1} + G_{k-2}]_i^{n+5/4} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} S_{i,k}^{n+5/4} \right) \quad (15b)$$

4.4.4 Fourth operator: $Q^{n+2} = L_{2x} Q^{n+3/2}$

This operator is similar to the first operator (L_{1x}), but the one-sided formulas are reversed. So, the predictor step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+7/4} = Q_{i,k}^{n+3/2} - \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta x} [-7F_i + 8F_{i+1} - F_{i+2}]_k^{n+3/2} \quad (16a)$$

The corrector step is:

$$Q_{i,k}^{n+2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{i,k}^{n+7/4} + Q_{i,k}^{n+3/2} - \frac{\Delta t}{6\Delta x} [7F_i - 8F_{i-1} + F_{i-2}]_k^{n+7/4} \right) \quad (16b)$$

4.4.5 Ghost points

Ghost (fictitious) points are needed at the boundaries. To find the necessary fluxes at these points, we use a third-order extrapolation as follows: At axial inflow (denoted by the axial grid index $i=1$), the flux F is interpolated during the L_{1x} and L_{2x} operators using:

$$F_{0,k} = 4F_{1,k} - 6F_{2,k} + 4F_{3,k} - F_{4,k} \quad (17a)$$

$$F_{-1,k} = 4F_{0,k} - 6F_{1,k} + 4F_{2,k} - F_{3,k} \quad (17b)$$

At axial outflow (denoted by the axial grid index $i = I \max$), the flux F is interpolated during the L_{1x} and L_{2x} operators using:

$$F_{I \max+1,k} = 4F_{I \max,k} - 6F_{I \max-1,k} + 4F_{I \max-2,k} - F_{I \max-3,k} \quad (17c)$$

$$F_{I_{max+2,k}} = 4F_{I_{max+1,k}} - 6F_{I_{max,k}} + 4F_{I_{max-1,k}} - F_{I_{max-2,k}} \quad (17d)$$

Similar formulas are used for extrapolating the flux G in the radial direction (for the L_{1r} and L_{2r} operators) at $k=1$ and $k=K$ max.

4.5 Boundary Treatment

Similar to the integration scheme, the boundary conditions treatment is very important in simulating noise emissions. We use characteristics-based, radiation, outflow, and centerline conditions that avoid nonphysical oscillations and allow acoustic and perturbation waves to leave the computational domain without reflection as in the realistic situation. The goal of any of these numerical boundary conditions is to find the local time derivatives of the primitive perturbation variables (i.e., $\partial p'/\partial t$, $\partial u'/\partial t$, $\partial v'/\partial t$, and $\partial p'/\partial t$) at the four boundaries of the problem domain. Using Eqn. (9), these values will then be transformed into the time derivatives of the unknown conservative perturbation variables, which in turn constitute the time derivative of the unknown vector $\{Q'\}$ so that the solution can be advanced in time on the boundaries.

4.5.1 Characteristics boundary condition and applied excitation

At the axial inflow boundary, and from the centerline to $r=4R_j$, an input hydrodynamic (non-propagating) periodic excitation is applied to represent the excitation in the experimental setup and to increase the periodicity in the propagation field. The experimental setup suggests the following form for this excitation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \rho'_{exc} \\ u'_{exc} \\ v'_{exc} \\ p'_{exc} \end{bmatrix} = \delta \text{Real} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \hat{\rho}(r) \\ \hat{u}(r) \\ 0 \\ \hat{p}(r) \end{bmatrix} \exp(-i\omega t) \right) \quad (18)$$

where δ is a scaling parameter and the angular frequency ω is related to the Strouhal number by:

$$\text{St} \equiv \frac{fD}{U_j} = \frac{\omega R_j}{\pi U_j} \quad (19)$$

where $f=\omega/2\pi$ is the cyclic frequency of the excitation, $D=2R_j$ is the jet diameter at the nozzle exit. We set the value of ω to correspond to $\text{St}=0.2$ as in the experimental case. The amplitude functions $\hat{\rho}(r)$, $\hat{u}(r)$, and $\hat{p}(r)$ are expected to have a Gaussian profile with a peak near $r=R_j$. We use the mean flow field to reduce these three functions into only one. To do this, we first introduce $\hat{p}(r)$ as:

$$\hat{p}(r) = \exp\left(-\ln(2)\left(\frac{r-\hat{r}}{0.1}\right)^2\right) \quad (20a)$$

where the coordinate \hat{r} is determined such that the radial numerical derivative of $\hat{p}(r)$ is zero (within an acceptable tolerance) at the centerline when computed using a one-sided difference expression of the used numerical scheme (i.e., satisfying the condition $7\hat{p}(r_1)-8\hat{p}(r_2)+\hat{p}(r_3)=0$, where $r_1=0$). With this technique, we set \hat{r} to $0.784R_j$. Then, $\hat{\rho}(r)$ and $\hat{u}(r)$ will be related to $\hat{p}(r)$ as:

$$\hat{\rho}(r) = \frac{\hat{p}(r)}{\mathfrak{R}(x_1, \hat{r})a(x_1, \hat{r})^2} \quad (20b)$$

$$\hat{u}(r) = \frac{\hat{p}(r)}{\mathfrak{R}(x_1, \hat{r})a(x_1, \hat{r})} \quad (20c)$$

In Eqns. (20b) and (20c), $\mathfrak{R}(x_1, \hat{r})$ and $a(x_1, \hat{r})$ are the mean density and acoustic speed (speed of sound) at the axial inflow boundary at $r=\hat{r}$. We know that the amplitude of the numerical excitation is related to the physical excitation induced by the glow-discharge exciter. However, since there is no quantitative relationship between the two, we introduce δ as a tuning parameter so that the resulting intensities of the calculated and measured acoustic fields are comparable. Based on this, we set a nondimensional δ to 0.03 in the normalized version of Eqn. (18), since we solve the normalized equations.

Equation (18) provides the contribution of the excitation to the time derivatives of the primitive perturbation variables. These will be added to other values that are computed using the characteristics-based boundary treatment of Thompson⁴⁶. In this treatment, if the flow is supersonic then the time derivatives of all primitive perturbation variables are zeros, whereas if it is subsonic then they have non-zero values that are related to the axial gradients of these variables calculated from the interior grid points.

4.5.2 Outflow boundary condition

The outflow treatment is applied at the axial far-field boundary when $M>0.01$, where M is the local mean axial Mach number. The treatment is based on the asymptotic analysis of the linearized Euler equations for a uniform one-dimensional mean flow, as given by Tam and Webb³⁴. The boundary condition is:

$$\frac{\partial p'_{out}}{\partial t} = -V(\theta) \left(\frac{x}{R} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial x} + \frac{r}{R} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial r} + \frac{p'}{R} \right) \quad (21a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho'_{out}}{\partial t} = -U \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{a^2} \left(\frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial p'}{\partial x} \right) \quad (21b)$$

$$\frac{\partial u'_{out}}{\partial t} = -U \frac{\partial u'}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{\mathfrak{R}} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial x} \quad (21c)$$

$$\frac{\partial v'_{out}}{\partial t} = -U \frac{\partial v'}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{\mathfrak{R}} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial r} \quad (21d)$$

where $R = \sqrt{x^2 + r^2}$ is the polar coordinate, $\theta = \arctan(r/x)$ is the emission angle, $V(\theta) = a(x/RM + \sqrt{1 - (r/RM)^2})$ is the effective velocity of propagation along the R -direction, a is the local mean acoustic speed, and M is the local mean axial Mach number. The boundary condition in Eqn. (21a) is identical to the one derived by and Enquist and Majda⁴⁷, and Bayliss and Turkel⁴⁸, who also performed asymptotic analysis of LEE for a uniform one-dimensional mean flow.

4.5.3 Radiation boundary condition

The radiation regime (only outgoing acoustic waves^{34,49}) includes the remaining portion of the axial inflow boundary, the entire radial boundary, and the remaining portion of the axial far-field boundary. The conventional radiation condition applies at these boundaries, which is:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{bmatrix} \rho'_{rad} \\ u'_{rad} \\ v'_{rad} \\ p'_{rad} \end{bmatrix} = -V(\theta) \left(\frac{x}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{bmatrix} \rho' \\ u' \\ v' \\ p' \end{bmatrix} + \frac{r}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \begin{bmatrix} \rho' \\ u' \\ v' \\ p' \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{R} \begin{bmatrix} \rho' \\ u' \\ v' \\ p' \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (22)$$

where R and $V(\theta)$ are same as in Eqn. (21a).

4.5.4 Centerline boundary condition

The boundary conditions at the centerline are:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \begin{bmatrix} \rho' \\ u' \\ p' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (23a)$$

$$v' = 0 \quad (23b)$$

To apply these conditions, ghost points are introduced on the other side of the centerline.

5 RESULTS

The conservative perturbation variables are directly resolved by integrating Eqns. (6a)–(6e) and then the perturbation primitive variables are evaluated in a post-processing step through Eqn. (10). As the simulation starts, perturbation waves develop in time and

Fig. 6—Contours of the calculated (dashed lines) and measured (solid lines) sound pressure levels.

eventually have a periodic pattern. The frequency of this pattern is the frequency of the applied excitation. They travel from the near field downstream in near-axial and oblique directions.

To validate the calculations, the perturbation pressure field is used to compute the acoustic field in terms of the sound pressure levels (in dB), where $SPL = 20 \log(p'_{RMS}/0.05p_{scale})$. The 0.05 factor is due to the fact that the pressure in the test chamber was 0.05 atmospheric pressure, thus the SPL is actually referenced to this ambient pressure rather than to the atmospheric one. In computing the acoustic field, the simulation was carried out for sufficiently long time to ensure steady-state periodic behavior is reached. The perturbation pressure field is averaged over N time steps and the root mean square is computed as:

$$p'_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_1^N (p')^2}{N}} \quad (24)$$

With 48,000 time steps, the nondimensional simulation time is 822 units, which includes about 40 wave periods. This also ensures that the waves have traversed the entire domain and steady-state periodic perturbation field is available for computing p'_{RMS} . The results are compared with available measurements^{22,23} in Fig. 6. Reasonable agreement is observed. The scaling perturbation pressure (p_{scale}) is $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ N/m}^2$. The directivity plot in Fig. 7 gives the SPL distribution over a range of emission angles, $\theta = \arctan(r/x)$. The directivity is given at a polar coordinate $R = \sqrt{x^2 + r^2} = 48R_j$, and compares satisfactorily with the measurements.

For the rest of the figures, the results are normalized with respect to reference values, which are the mean jet density and velocity at the nozzle exit: \mathfrak{R}_j and U_j . This is a better representation of the order-of-magnitude of the perturbation solution. In Fig. 8, the evolutions of the perturbed pressure at eight different points (located at different radial and axial positions are given). The perturbed signals settle quickly to a periodic function. The amplitude of the perturbation decays in the radial

Fig. 7—Directivity from calculated (line) and measured (squares) acoustic field at $R/R_j = 48$.

direction. There is a phase shift between the perturbation pressure waves recorded at different radial locations. This is a result of the distances between them, which are traveled by the wave in finite times. Figure 9 illustrates the propagation process of the perturbation pressure waves (acoustic waves), where snapshots of the perturbation pressure field are given at

Fig. 8—Temporal development of the normalized perturbed pressure at different spatial points.

Fig. 9—Two-dimensional propagation of the pressure waves at 6,000; 12,000; and 18,000 Δt .

successive instants until the waves traverse the entire domain. This figure indicates directional pattern of propagation. Acoustic wave fronts form an angle of about 30° with the x -axis. This figure also manifests the favorable performance of the boundary conditions treatment, where the domain boundaries are nearly transparent to the waves as they leave the domain. The centerline boundary conditions (with the ghost points) are satisfied well. The radial gradient is zero at the centerline although the peaks of the travelling waves downstream are not located at the centerline. This is interpreted as a result of the excitation profile, which peaks at a small but non-zero value of r . In fact, this feature of free jets was observed in other studies even for natural (unexcited) jets^{10,36}. This implies that naturally-induced excitation from the nozzle have similar profile to the applied excitation here, with the peak of the ‘natural’ excitation forming an annular layer rather than being at the centerline. Figure 10

Fig. 10—Variations of the RMS normalized perturbation pressure at different radial distances.

shows the axial distribution of the RMS perturbation pressure at different radial distances. Near the center-line, there is a region of concentrated perturbation at about $25R_j$ after the nozzle. The oscillations in p'_{RMS} at $r=R_j$ are believed to be physical and not due to numerical effects. This is supported by the nature of these variations, which do not have high spatial frequency as would be expected in case of spurious oscillations with the solution having small but sharp variations from one grid point to another. Also, the other curve that corresponds to $r=5R_j$ has comparable amplitude of the one corresponding to $r=R_j$; however, there are no such variations at this radial distance. Similar behavior was reported in a previous study by Shih et al.⁵⁰, in which they predicted the flow field and noise of a supersonic heated jet, Mach 2, using a coupled LSS/Kirchhoff-method approach (LSS stands for large-scale simulation, which is related to LES but with three decomposed flow fields rather than two). These perturbations are limited to the critical mixing layer (behind the nozzle lip) at the peak time-averaged perturbation amplitude. Figures 11–14 show the axial variations of the perturbation of the pressure, axial velocity component, radial velocity component, and density; respectively. Comparing these figures shows that the location of the peak amplitude, or saturation, of the velocity and density perturbations is at about twice the distance of the peak pressure perturbation. This is a difference in the propagation of these waves from the acoustic propagation. It should be mentioned here that these waves still have same wavelength, which is in agreement with the linear stability theory. On the other hand, such difference in the peak locations of the perturbation waves cannot be predicted by this theory. While the measured data do not include similar figures (thus cannot confirm this feature we found through our

Fig. 11—Variations of the normalized perturbation of pressure at different radial distances.

simulations), such a feature has been reported in other simulations of free jets, such as the study by Lew et al.⁵¹, who used LES to predict the noise of a subsonic Mach 0.9 jet with Re 100,000. The jet was excited in a different approach than the one followed here. They applied random perturbations in the form of induced velocities from a vortex ring with a radius of R_j at $x=R_j$. The axial locations of the peak u'_{RMS} was different from the location of the peak v'_{RMS} (the axial variation of p'_{RMS} was not presented), both at a radial distance of $r=R_j$.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The development of the perturbation field for a high-speed jet flow subject to hydrodynamic excitation was simulated by a two-step method. We chose this problem since it was studied experimentally before (the

Fig. 12—Variations of the normalized perturbation of axial velocity at different radial distances.

Fig. 13—Variations of the normalized perturbation of radial velocity at different radial distances.

excitation was used to enhance the periodic component of the perturbation field) but we would like to numerically examine further details that were not covered by the experimental study. The goal is to test this method (as an efficient alternative to relatively more-demanding strategies, such as DNS and LES) in solving this problem and then to explore more details about the perturbation fields and the radiated jet noise. The first step in the presented method was to model the steady mean flow through an analytical technique that includes curve fitting, conservation of mass and momentum, and the equation of state. This technique could reproduce the features of the mean flow well. The second step in the presented method was to numerically integrate the linearized Euler equations to calculate the perturbation field. The conservative perturbation field was computed first and then the primitive perturbation

Fig. 14—Variations of the normalized perturbation of density at different radial distances.

variables were extracted. The resolved perturbation field was validated by comparing the calculated acoustic field to corresponding measurements. Then, the temporal and spatial developments of the density, velocity (axial and radial), and acoustic (pressure) waves were examined, covering details that were not provided in the experiments. The acoustic waves are emitted from the region after the uniform core, where the perturbation of the pressure reaches its maximum. These waves follow a preferred directional pattern. All perturbation variables exhibit periodic pattern after the initial transient is passed. Also, they all decay in the radial direction. However, the saturation point (axial location of the peak of the travelling wave) of the pressure (acoustic) waves occurs at a different distance from that of the velocities and density waves.

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